

AN EVALUATION OF TEST METHODS FOR DETERMINING ADHESIVE SHEAR STRESS-STRAIN PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

While the aviation industry is increasingly making use of composite structure to realize reduced air vehicle cost and weight, obtaining certification of adhesively bonded structure has been difficult to achieve to date because of adhesive bonding concerns. Specifically, the material qualification methods for the adhesives and the certification approach for adhesive joints are not well-established, limiting bonded joint acceptance. The current American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) industry standard for the measurement of structural adhesive shear stress-strain properties, ASTM D5656, employs the use of an antiquated contact extensometer (KGR-1). Since the method employs contact measurement, the system compliance is quantified and subtracted from the data through the use of a metal standard. Consequently, measurement error is greatly dependent on the precision and accuracy of the extensometer placement for the metal standard and the test specimen. The complications involved with this test method often lead to unnecessary conservatism in joint design. Furthermore, in the last few decades, improvement in image processing with microcomputers has caused non-contact measurement techniques to become increasingly popular in the experimental test community. The objective of this effort was to evaluate a variety of strain measurement techniques, including digital image correlation (DIC), moiré interferometry, and contact extensometers, and generate comparative adhesive property data with the overall goal of providing an improved test method approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aerospace industry is continuously striving to reduce fuel consumption costs and increase range. As a result, commercial and military production programs feature airframes that can exceed 65 percent composite by weight, although 15 to 40 percent is more representative of the wider aeroindustry [1]. Unfortunately, the full weight-saving benefits of composite structures has not yet been realized for unitized structure due a lack of confidence in adhesively bonded joints. Concerns with adhesive bonding include poorly established qualification and certification methodology, process controls, inspection techniques and design criteria. This paper is focused on the improvement of the qualification methodology, specifically dealing with the evaluation of test methods for the quantification of adhesive shear stress-strain design allowables and emphasizing the linear elastic region for design. Three measurement devices were evaluated: Digital Image Correlation (DIC), moiré interferometry, and an industry-accepted contact extensometer (KGR-1). Ultimately, the intent of this effort is to find a replacement technique for the KGR-1 extensometer prescribed in American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) industry standard ASTM D5656 [2].

inch) from the edge of the machined notches. Overlap, width and bondline thickness data were recorded with an accuracy of ± 0.0025 mm (0.0001 inch).

Figure 2: Specimen fiducial marks

2.2 KGR-1 MEASUREMENT

The ASTM D5656 standard draws heavily on the technique developed by Raymond Krieger at American Cyanamid (now CEM) for the in-situ measurement of adhesive properties. One of the most important facets of Krieger's technique was the use of linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) KGR-1 extensometers for measurement of adhesive shear deformations. The KGR-1 device measures the relative displacement between two points using a three-point configuration. Displacement measurements are derived from the two LVDT extensometers which were fixed to the specimens using tension generated from a ball-chain leaf-spring connection on the two extensometers (Figure 3).

Figure 3: KGR-1 extensometer mounted on calibrating tool

The strain contribution resulting from the aluminum adherends was quantified by collecting stress-strain data on a solid aluminum specimen with the same dimensions as the bonded specimen. The aluminum specimen was loaded to a static load of 4448 N (1000 lbf), and data were recorded for approximately 30 seconds. This procedure was repeated five times prior to testing the bonded specimens. The bonded specimens were tested using a displacement rate of 0.33 mm (0.013 inch)/min which roughly correlates to the 2447 N (550 lbf)/min load rate specified in ASTM D5656. Data were collected at a rate of 10 Hz using National Instruments' LabVIEW data acquisition software.

The extensometers were calibrated using the calibration device depicted in Figure 4. The calibration device consisted of two thick aluminum plates mounted on a Starrett Co. micrometer with ± 0.0025 mm (0.0001 inch) resolution. One aluminum plate was fixed while the other could translate linearly. The micrometer displacement was coupled to the mobile plate through the spring-loaded spindle. The extensometers were placed on the calibration device, the LVDT core was adjusted to zero the voltage output, and the micrometer was incrementally adjusted to a known displacement. A calibration look-up table was developed for each extensometer by recording the scaled output signal using the LabVIEW data acquisition software for displacement increments of 0.025 mm (0.001 inch) in the range of 0 to 0.64 mm (0.025 inch). Each incremental displacement was held for 30 seconds to obtain an average reading. A new set of calibration tables was developed for each day and after testing a specimen to failure. A calibration recall test was periodically performed each day. The

calibration recall test used the calibration device to check the voltage output and compare to the initial look-up table.

Figure 4: KGR-1 calibration device [6]

KGR-1 tests were conducted under ambient 20-22°C (68-72°F) temperature. Most tests were conducted in the linear elastic region only up to 4448 N (1000 lbf). Data were analyzed using the ASTM D5656 procedure in which the relative displacement between B and C is measured with the KGR-1 device (Figure 5). The extensometer point attached at A is used for alignment purposes because the joint region rotates during loading. Therefore, the KGR-1 measurement represents the relative displacement between B and C in the x'-direction, or "KGR" direction (parallel to the adherend-adhesive interface), as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: KGR-1 location points, including fiducial marks [7]

Figure 6: Zoomed view of gage section under load [7]

The governing equations for the KGR-1 calculations are as follows [3]. The apparent adhesive shear strain, γ_{apparent} , which is used to calculate shear modulus is determined by

$$\gamma_{\text{apparent}} = \frac{da - dm}{t} \quad (1)$$

where t is the adhesive thickness, d_a is the relative displacement between B and C in the KGR direction of the specimen, and d_m is the displacement in the solid aluminum specimen.

Parameter, d_m , is calculated from

$$d_m = \frac{p-t}{p} M \frac{L}{1000} \quad (2)$$

where M is the relative displacement between B and C in the KGR direction of the solid aluminum specimen at 4448 N (1000 lbf), t is the aluminum “bondline” thickness (distance between E and F), p is the distance between B and C, and L is load at displacement d_a .

The average adhesive shear stress, $\tau_{average}$, is calculated by

$$\tau_{average} = \frac{P}{Lb} \quad (3)$$

where P is the applied tensile load, L is the overlap length, and b is the width of the specimen. After the apparent stress and strain are obtained, the linear shear modulus $G_{adhesive}$ is then calculated as

$$G_{adhesive} = \frac{\tau_{average}}{\gamma_{apparent}} \quad (4)$$

The adhesive shear stress-strain response can be described with reference to three key areas: LL, the point of linear limit; KN, the knee; and UL, or ultimate limit as shown by a typical curve in Figure 7. All data analysis was performed on digital data following guidelines set by ASTM D5656 with the exception of the assignment of the knee point. In this effort, for specimens tested to failure, the knee was assigned by drawing a line through the stress-strain curve roughly bisecting the angle between the two tangents for the elastic and the yielded regions.

Figure 7: Typical adhesive shear stress-strain curve [8]

2.3 DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

As a comparison to the KGR-1 contact extensometers, non-contact measurement techniques were evaluated with the thick adherend specimen bonded with FM 73 adhesive. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is a non-contact, full-field displacement measurement technique. Although it has been researched since the early 1980's, DIC has gained popularity in the last decade, especially in the fields of experimental mechanics. DIC tracks the movement of points on the surface of an object while the object is loaded to produce a displacement field. In this study, the specimen bonded surfaces under investigation were prepared with a white aerosol spray paint and then overcoated with black toner to create a random structure. The speckles were generally considered to be physically attached to the specimen. As load was applied to the specimen, the surfaces moved, and the position and the irradiance of the pattern are changed under incoherent white light. The displacements could then be easily obtained by matching different zones of two images captured before and after loading of the

specimen. This image processing was then accomplished by digitizing the images captured by a camera system, analyzing the intensity distribution before and after loading of the specimen, and performing then necessary calculations with suitable algorithms. In this work, Correlated Solutions' Vic 3-D 2007 software program and 5 Megapixel 2448 x 2048 pixel Nikon CCD cameras fitted with Nikon AF Micro Nikkor 60 mm lens (and Kenko extension tube for some tests) were used for 3-D stereomicroscopic imaging.

In this effort, moiré interferometry testing was conducted on a specimen prior to testing the same specimen with DIC. After moiré data had been obtained, the in-house manufactured load frame was removed from its stand, and a fine speckle pattern was applied to the test specimen overtop of the moiré grating. The coating was 0.021 mm (0.00083 in) thick. Specimens were not removed from the load frame in between moiré and DIC testing. The cameras were mounted approximately 25.4 cm (1 inch) from the specimen with a separation around 4.44 cm (1.75 in), positioned somewhat symmetrically about the specimen. A Techniquip FOI-250 fiber optic light source provided illumination for the test. Focus, aperture, and exposure time were adjusted to ensure image sharpness and brightness and then fixed for calibration and testing (Figure 8). Calibration was accomplished after specimen testing, and the load frame was moved out of the area. Approximately 20 calibration photos of a 0.28 or 0.44 mm (0.011 or 0.017 in) (dot spacing) calibration target were acquired with significant grid rotation. Calibration data were analyzed with Vic 3-D software. To begin testing, several initial specimen reference images were captured to account for distortion correction. Tests were conducted under ambient laboratory conditions, and one image was acquired at a null load, roughly 890 N (200 lbf), and at 445-N (100-lbf) increments up to 4448 N (1000 lbf). Acquisition intervals were 250 ms. The specimen was unloaded, and another measurement was made at the null load condition. Although ASTM D5656 recommends a rate of 2455 N (550 lbf)/min, the loading rate was either 4448 N (1000 lbf)/min or 1668 N (375 lbf)/min. Both the solid aluminum standard and the bonded specimen were tested with DIC. Correlations were performed in Vic-3D for an area of interest (AOI) which was approximately 4.76 mm (0.1875 in), or half of the width of the overlap area using a subset size of 51 pixels and a step size of 7 pixels. Subset size controls the area of the image that is used to track the displacement between images. It was set to be large enough to ensure that there is a sufficiently distinctive pattern contained in the area used for correlation while the step size controls the spacing of the points that are analyzed during correlation. Data were further reduced and post processed using Noesy's Fortner Transform software instead of Vic-3D.

Figure 8: 3-D DIC Experimental Set-up

2.4 MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY

Testing was also conducted via moiré interferometry to generate accurate in-plane displacement measurements. As a non-contact, full-field optical technique, moiré interferometry uses a physical diffraction grating imprinted onto the surface of the specimen and a virtual reference grating created by the interaction of two coherent laser beams of light. As the reference grating interacts with the specimen grating, interference patterns captured via a camera (same as was used for DIC) produce patterns of dark and light fringes, which are lines of constant displacement. The 4-beam moiré

interferometer set-up is shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. One laser with a 4-way beam splitter illuminates the specimen during testing, and 2-beams at a time are blocked allowing evaluation of the U displacement field or the V displacement field as needed. Automated phase-shifting fringe analysis was accomplished using Superfringe2, an in-house program developed by Dr. David Mollenhauer.

Figure 9. Moiré Interferometry Experimental Set-up

Figure 10. Moiré Interferometry Specimen Test

After general test specimen fabrication, specimens were prepared for moiré interferometry testing by replication of a high-frequency, cross-line diffraction grating. The basic grating replication technique is shown in Figure 11. An AFRL-developed process was used for grating alignment. The grating layer was 0.092 mm (0.0036 in) thick. For testing, a specimen was mounted into self-aligning grips fabricated in-house. The specimen was coupled to the load frame using a fixture, spacers as required, and a tight-fit 12.7 mm (0.5 inch) loading pin (omitting the angle-cut steel bushing recommended in ASTM D5656). The load frame, also specially designed in-house, was an electrically-powered, screw-driven machine controlled by a Newport Model ESP300 universal controller. Once the specimen was mounted, the rigid-body rotation was adjusted. A null load of 890 N (200 lbf) was selected. Photos were taken initially to establish a baseline scale and alignment for comparison during and after loading conditions. Acquisition time was 250 ms, for a 3-4 sec acquisition interval. At this time, the location of a fiducial mark was recorded, and the rigid-body rotation was again adjusted in attempts to enable fringe resolution of the specimen bondline under higher loading conditions without additional rotation. The specimen was loaded, and a series of photos were captured in both the U and V fields. Phase-shifting was applied during the acquisition of fringe patterns to enable automated fringe analysis with Superfringe2. The process was repeated and data collected during specimen loading and unloading at 2669 N (600 lbf) and 4448 N (1000 lbf), using the fiducial marks to re-establish the coordinate system for easier data processing. Both the solid aluminum standard and the bonded specimen were tested under ambient laboratory conditions. Testing was repeated on the bonded specimen (referred to as Test 1 and Test 2) to demonstrate consistency.

Moiré data were imported into Superfringe2 for fringe analyses. The relationships for every x, y point in the field of view are shown below [9]:

$$U(x, y) = \frac{1}{2f_s} N_x(x, y),$$

$$V(x, y) = \frac{1}{2f_s} N_y(x, y) \quad (5)$$

In this moiré interferometry application, $f_s = 1200$ lines/mm. In the fringe patterns, the contour interval is $1/2f_s$, which is $0.417 \mu\text{m}$ displacement per fringe order. The sensitivity is its reciprocal, 2.4 fringes per micrometer displacement.

After displacement data were obtained, the data were analyzed via RSI Transform software. The data were scaled (each pixel was approximately 0.00225 mm), and a coordinate system was oriented such that the center of the bondline in the gage section of the specimen was roughly the origin. Corrupt data were removed; then data were smoothed, manipulated to remove rigid-body rotations, and further post processed for the loading cases.

Figure 11. Basic Grating Application Process [10]

3 RESULTS

3.1 KGR-1 EXTENSOMETER EVALUATION

The extensometer was calibrated using the calibration device depicted in Figure 4, and a calibration look-up table was developed as described in Subsection 2.2. The specimens were tested at ambient conditions. The standard suggests reporting data based on the analysis of a representative curve formed by the averaging of data points from both sides of the KGR-1 extensometer. However, detailed investigation of the initial KGR-1 extensometer data revealed inconsistencies between the two sides of the KGR-1 extensometer both within the same test (i.e. between each side of the KGR-1) and between cyclic tests performed on the same specimen. Of particular interest was the large coefficient of variation for the moduli ranging from 17-30%. It was initially unclear whether the large variation was due to extensometer placement or an inherent error resulting from extensometer resolution in the low strain region. To determine the cause of error, a single specimen (Figure 12) was loaded and unloaded to approximately 4448 N (1000 lbf) for multiple cycles. Between each test, the extensometer LVDT core was manually zeroed by threading or unthreading the core rod. The stress-strain curves for two tests are provided in Figure 12. The type of test is annotated at the end of the sample identification (ID), where “NTF” signifies elastic region tests and each referenced extensometer side (Port A, Starboard B, and average). The fitted line indicating the modulus is included to visually show the disparity between each side and test (NTF and NTF-4).

Investigation of Figure 12 seems to indicate the cause for variation in the modulus results may be the effect of the extensometer resolution and rotation induced displacements rather than the initial placement of the extensometer. With regard to rotation induced displacements, Tomblin et al [7] described similar findings which led to the implementation of a fourth contact point in their KGR-type extensometer. Figure 6 depicts the typical load-induced rotation in the gage section of the specimen.

Although the rotation induced displacement error is unavoidable with the KGR-1 device due to the lack of a fourth pin, the error induced from the low displacement resolution could be reduced. Calibration diagnostic tests were performed to determine if the implementation of a fine resolution calibration would reduce error in the elastic strain region. In these tests, the KGR -1 was calibrated by constructing a look-up table of voltage output for discrete displacements. The first calibration file was constructed using the ASTM recommended displacement increment of 0.025 mm (0.001 inch). The second calibration file was constructed using a finer step size of 0.0025 mm (0.0001 inch) from 0 to 0.025 mm (0.001 inch) followed by a coarser step size. The calibration diagnostic with the finer step size did slightly improve the low end accuracy (from 9% error to 2% at 0.0152 mm (0.0006 in) and

decrease the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). However, the relative error in the sub-0.0102 mm (0.0004 inch) displacement region may still be a source of error in the linear elastic region.

Figure 12: FM 73 shear stress-strain curve (Specimen K2-1)

After baseline testing, KGR-1 testing was conducted with the thick adherend specimen bonded with FM 73 adhesive and the solid aluminum standard using the finer step size calibration file. In one instance, the average signal of both extensometers was used to calculate the shear modulus. The remaining NTF tests used side A only. Side B was not used for this analysis since the majority of the scaled output was below the 0.0051 mm (0.0002 inch) threshold where the SNR is quite large. Test set 2 used the ASTM standard steel bushing for load centering (in attempts to eliminate the load eccentricity) while Test set 1 did not. Results are in Table 1.

Test Set	Test ID	Extensometer	Shear Modulus MPa [psi]	R2
1	K2-1_NTF-4_20150318	Average	428 [62100]	0.992
	K2-1_NTF-3_20150318	KGR A	536 [77700]	0.993
	K2-1_NTF-2_20150318	KGR A	410 [59500]	0.986
	K2-1_NTF_20150318	KGR A	616 [89300]	0.985
	Average			498 [72200]
CoV [%]			19%	
2	K2-1-B_NTF-4_20150320	KGR A	508 [73600]	0.987
	K2-1-B_NTF-3_20150320	KGR A	243 [35200]	0.945
	K2-1-B_NTF-2_20150320	KGR A	271 [39400]	0.957
	K2-1-B_NTF_20150320	KGR A	404 [58600]	0.990
	Average			357 [51700]
CoV [%]			34%	

Table 1: Shear stress-strain results from FM 73 tested at ambient conditions

3.2 DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

DIC testing was conducted with the thick adherend specimen bonded with FM 73 adhesive and the solid aluminum standard. Representative images for the test specimen under the maximum applied load of 4448 N (1000 lbf) are shown in Figure 13 with the two camera system. It should be noted Camera 1 exhibited much more noise as compared to the other Camera 0.

Figure 13: Typical DIC speckle pattern at maximum load a) Camera 0 and b) Camera 1

Noesys Fortner Transform software was used for data manipulation and visualization applications instead of Vic-3D to ensure the same coordinate system and AOI were established to compare the DIC tests to the moiré tests. A coordinate system was established for data analysis using the center of the specimen in the bondline as the origin (Figure 14). It should be noted to use Vic-3D analysis special procedures must be developed to account for rigid body rotation (i.e. identify all four fiducial marks in AOI and use the overlap distance for coordinate system development). Full-field displacement data were analyzed from the left-hand side machined notch to the origin and approximately ± 1.5 mm (0.059 inch) in the V-direction. Displacement data for the test specimen under the maximum applied load as compared to the null load are shown as contour maps in Figure 15 where the U and V fields represent the horizontal and vertical displacement fields, respectively. The displacement range and contour spacing are noted below the figures. Although not shown, some out-of-plane displacement was observed (± 0.0012 mm). Figure 15b. graphically depicts the subset size of 39 pixels, and the pixel size is roughly 0.0072 mm. This is related to the spatial resolution and noise sensitivity of the measurement process [11]. The full-field strain results are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 14: Specimen coordinate system

Figure 15: DIC displacement field at maximum load a) horizontal U-field, b) DIC subset size (U-field), and c) vertical V-field

Figure 16: DIC shear strain results at maximum load

3.3 MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY

Two tests were conducted in which the same specimen was loaded to 4448 N (1000 lbf). The same coordinate system implemented for DIC testing was used with the moiré testing. Typical moiré fringe patterns for the test specimen under applied loads are shown in Figure 17 and Figure 18 where the U and V fields represent the horizontal and vertical displacement fields, respectively. These fringe patterns were obtained by introducing a carrier pattern of rotation to enable fringe gradients in the adhesive zone to be resolved. It is apparent in the null load case that the fringe patterns for U and V fields are smooth and almost symmetrical about the bondline. As the specimen is loaded, larger deformation is observed in both directions. Moiré contour maps obtained from the experiments show the displacement range (Figure 19). The fiducial marks in the specimen appear as corrupt data. In addition, there were some imperfections in the grating, evident by a lack of data. Two tests were conducted, and these data are reproducible. Viscoelastic behavior is observed after one test (Figure 20). Good reproducibility between two tests is observed from Figure 20. The full-field strain results are shown in Figure 21. In general, better resolution is observed as compared to DIC testing. This can be seen visually in both the displacement (Figure 15 vs. Figure 19) and shear strain (Figure 16 vs. Figure 22) results.

Figure 17: Typical moiré fringe pattern at null load a) horizontal U-field and b) vertical V-field

Figure 18: Typical moiré fringe pattern at maximum load a) horizontal U-field and b) vertical V-field

Figure 19: Moiré contour map at maximum load a) horizontal U-field and b) vertical V-field for Test 1

Figure 20: Moiré test validation: a) contour map: difference in initial null load of 890 N (200 lbf) before and after test, and b) shear strain results: difference between Test 1 and Test 2

Figure 21: Moiré shear strain results at maximum load for Test 1

3.4 COMPARISON OF TECHNIQUES

Based on the evaluations of the techniques, some observations can be made. DIC was much less time consuming from sample preparation, testing, and analysis of results as compared to moiré or KGR-1. However, there is significant lack of insight into the correlation and analysis algorithms. Also, an increase in noise and data scatter was apparent in the DIC testing. Both moiré and DIC data were taken from a random cut roughly in the centerline through the thickness of the specimen. A comparison of the data is shown in Figure 22. This figure displays the differences between the two techniques when examining the displacements between a line average of the fiducial points. The data are comparable. Minimal change in displacement is noted until reaching the bondline. A comparison of the average shear stress-strain results for all three approaches is tabulated in Table 2. The average shear modulus obtained from the KGR-1 is significantly lower as compared to the moiré and DIC results. The moiré and DIC results are within 7%. The manufacturer’s published KGR-1 data for this adhesive reports a shear modulus of 842 MPa (122000 psi) [2], roughly 75% of the full-field

techniques; however, variation in shear modulus due to KGR-1 testing is apparent; other published data for FM 73 is 605 MPa (87800 psi) [12] while the KGR-1 data in this study yields 427 MPa (61900 psi).

Figure 22: Comparison of moiré and DIC shear strain results roughly through thickness of the specimen in the centerline

Test Type	Shear Modulus MPa [psi]
KGR-1 Extensometer	427 [61900]
DIC	1185 [172000]
Moiré	1107 [160000]

Table 2: Comparison of shear stress-strain results from FM 73 tested at ambient conditions

4 CONCLUSIONS

Three different test methods were investigated for the determination of in-situ adhesive properties using a thick adherend lap shear specimen. The challenges associated with ASTM D5656 and the KGR-1 extensometer, particularly when studying the linear elastic region, are great. Difficulties are encountered from load eccentricity and rigid body rotation, device point slippage, and insufficient calibration procedures in the area of interest, resulting in appreciable error in test measurement and data analysis procedures. The aim of this effort was to determine how to use DIC as a full-field displacement method as a KGR-1 extensometer replacement technique. Moiré interferometry was used to provide accurate full-field displacement measurements, but test specimen preparation and analysis of results are very tedious, time consuming, and extremely sensitive. Therefore, it is not an amenable replacement technique. Preliminary results indicate similar trends in strain data between moiré and DIC, approximately 65% higher modulus than that obtained from the KGR-1, although there is lower spatial resolution with DIC. DIC and moiré agree in displacement measurement trends as well, but anomalies can exist possibly due to rotational correction differences in data analysis. Preliminary results are encouraging, but further testing is needed to vet out robust DIC test measurement and data analysis procedures.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. Red, The market for OOA aerocomposites, *High Performance Composites*, March 2014.
- [2] FM 73 Film Adhesive Technical Data Sheet, Cytec Engineered Materials, 11 August 2011.
- [3] ASTM D5656, Standard test method for thick-adherend metal lap-shear joints for determination of the stress-strain behavior of adhesives in shear by tension loading, *ASTM International*, 2010.
- [4] ASTM D3933-98, Standard guide for preparation of aluminum surfaces for structural adhesives bonding (phosphoric acid anodizing), *ASTM International*, 2010.
- [5] J. Mazza, K. Storage, D. McCray, J. Smith, The evaluation of adhesive bond primers for repair bonding of aluminum alloys, *Proceedings of the 42nd International SAMPE Technical Conference*, Salt Lake City, UT, 11-14 October 2010.
- [6] KGR-1 Extensometer Operating Manual, American Cyanamid Company.
- [7] C. Yang, H. Huang, J. S. Tomblin, D. W. Oplinger, Evaluation and adjustments for ASTM D 5656 standard test method for thick-adherend metal lap-shear joints for determination of the stress-strain behavior of adhesives in shear by tension loading, *Journal of Testing and Evaluation*, JTEVA, Vol. 29, No. 1, January 2001, pp. 36-43.
- [8] M. Tsai, J. Morton, R. Krieger, D. Oplinger, Experimental investigation of the thick-adherend lap-shear test, *Journal of Advanced Materials*, Vol. 27, No. 3, April 1996, pp. 28-36.
- [9] D. Post, B. Han, and P. Ifju, *High Sensitivity Moiré: Experimental Analysis for Mechanics and Materials*, Springer-Verlag Inc., New York, 1994.
- [10] D. Post, R. Czarnek, J. D. Wood, and D. Joh, Deformations and strains in a thick-adherend lap joint, *Adhesively Bonded Joints: Testing, Analysis, and Design. ASTM STP 981*. W. S. Johnson, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1988, pp. 107-118.
- [11] R. J. Davidson, A Comparison of Moiré Interferometry and Digital Image Correlation, M. Thesis AFIT/GAE/ENY08-M06, Air Force Institute of Technology, 2008.
- [12] J. Tomblin, W. Seneviratne, P. Escobar, Y. Yoon-Khian, Shear stress-strain data for structural adhesives, *DOT/FAA/AR-02/97*, U.S. Dept of Transportation FAA, November 2002.